

Original Article

Ficus Benjamina Leaves Derived Cellulose Scaffolds for Regeneration of Full Thickness Skin Wound in New Zealand White Rabbits

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The main aim of this study was to prepare *Ficus benjamina* leaves derived cellulose scaffolds by treatment with 5% SDS followed by incubation in 1% TnBP solution for 48h and finally soaked in 4% NaOCl for 36h and these scaffolds were evaluated for the regeneration of full thickness skin wound in New Zealand white rabbits. After general anesthesia and preparation of surgical site, the full thickness wounds were created on the dorsum and remained open, reconstructed with autograft, decellularized leaf scaffold and powdered decellularized leaf scaffold in group I, II, III and IV, respectively. The warmth of the wound area was significantly ($P < 0.05$) increased on day 7, 14 and 21 in group I, II and III animals and on day 7 and 14 in group IV animals. However, warmth of the adjoining area was significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher on day 7, 14 and 21 in group I and II, and on day 7 and 14 in group III and IV animals. On day 21, wound completely healed in group III and IV animals. A significant ($P < 0.05$) increase in neutrophil counts after creation of wound and transplantation of scaffold was observed on day 7 in all the animals of different groups. Histopathological observations showed complete epithelization and organized collagen formation on day 28 in group III and IV. DAPI stained and SEM analysis of tissues also showed host tissue infiltration within the scaffold. It was concluded that the decellularized *Ficus benjamina* leaves scaffold can be used for regeneration of full thickness skin defects.

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Introduction

The scarcity of transplantable organs and tissues has always been an issue, but it has hardly gotten any worse. In addition to human-to-human organ and tissue transplantation, xenotransplantation and tissue engineering are currently the main treatments for the paucity of organs and tissues available for transplant. Employing transplanted cells, tissues, or organs from animals like pigs, xenotransplantation reduces the need for human donors [1]. Despite the fact that plants and animals use essentially distinct strategies to move fluids, chemicals, and macromolecules, their vascular networks surprisingly resemble one another. The most prevalent biodegradable natural polymer, cellulose, has been the subject of much research in the area of biomaterials over the past

few years because of its widespread availability, lack of moral dilemmas, inexpensive cost, biocompatibility, and adaptable biomechanical characteristics [2]. Comparable to animal cells' extracellular matrix (ECM), plant cell walls control the growth and division of individual cells [3]. Strength and flexibility are provided by the cellulose polymers' because of many hydrogen bonds and low intermolecular attractive forces [4]. Especially for clinical usage, neurological and cardiovascular regeneration, as well as bone and cartilage repair, cellulose-based biomaterials have found extensive use in the biomedical area as nanoparticles, fibers, and composites made from them [2,5-7].

As the first barrier against environment offends, the skin has a vital physiological function. The skin is the largest organ of the mammalian body and, acts as a protective barrier against detrimental environmental threats like trauma, radiation and microbial infection. The skin may be damaged by acute or chronic

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wounds, burn, diabetic, pressure and venous ulcers. In most cases, small skin wounds are treated by applying dressings and healed either by primary closure or by second intension. But large skin defects require adequate wound dressing/skin grafts and skin substitutes to accelerate the healing process. Autologous skin flap transplantation is the gold standard procedure for reconstruction of skin defects but it causes donor site morbidity [8]. In the case of dermal tissue defects, fibroblasts secrete immature extracellular matrix (ECM) into the wound area, leading to the formation of scars. A newly formed epidermis cannot establish close contact with dermal tissue, because a new basement membrane cannot be established [9]. Allografts and xenografts may elicit severe immune reaction as compared to autografts [10]. In order to deal with these problems, the researchers started to work on development of tissue engineered scaffolds for the management of large wounds. Biological scaffold materials composed of extracellular matrix (ECM) have been used for reconstruction of skin defects and hernia in ruminants and equine [11-13]. Decellularized plant tissues have great potential for cellulose-based scaffold materials due to mimicry of plant and animal vascular network structures [14]. Decellularized plant leaves scaffolds may be the best substitute for reconstruction of skin defects.

In the present study *Ficus benjamina* leaves were chosen for its morphological structure, which may provide a platform for the host cells to adhere and spread. The main aim of this study was the evaluation of *Ficus benjamina* leaves derived cellulose scaffolds for regeneration of full thickness skin wound in New Zealand white rabbits.

Materials and Methods

In the present study, the native *Ficus benjamina* leaves were decellularized using 5% concentrations of sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS) for 120h followed by incubation in 1% Tri-n-butyl phosphate (TnBP) for 48h and finally bleach by 4% sodium hypochlorite (36h). The decellularized leaves scaffolds were characterization by hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) staining, 4,6-diamidino-2-phenylindole 2HCl (DAPI) staining, scanning electron microscopic (SEM) analysis and deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) quantification.

Hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) staining

Hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) staining was used to observe and detect the cellular cytoplasm and nucleus components of the decellularized *Ficus benjamina* leaves samples.

DAPI (4,6-diamidino-2-phenylindole 2HCl) fluorescent staining

The decellularized *Ficus benjamina* leaves sections were rehydrated and then washed with 0.2% tris buffered saline tween-20 (TBS-T) three times. Thereafter, the samples were stained with DAPI solution (200µl) and incubated for 10 minute in dark place at room temperature and observed under a fluorescent microscope. If nuclei were detected, they fluoresced a cold blue color [15].

Scanning electron microscopy

For surface morphology characterization of the decellularized *Ficus benjamina* leaves scaffolds by using the SEM Carl-Zeiss, EVO-18. The samples were fixed in 2.5% glutaraldehyde, transferred in serial graded ethanol and finally submerged in Hexamethyl disilazane (HMDS) for complete dehydration. The dehydrated samples were coated with a thin layer of gold-Palladium at 180° (15 mA for 5 minutes). Finally specimens were observed under SEM at 10 kV and ultramicrographs were taken from different locations [16].

DNA quantification

DNA extraction and quantification of the decellularized *Ficus benjamina* leaves scaffolds was done by using cetyltrimethyl ammonium bromide (C-TAB)-based method [17]. The total amount of the DNA was quantified using spectrophotometry (NanoDrop ND1000).

In vivo implantation

Six clinically healthy adult New Zealand white rabbits of either sex were used in this study. The proposed research protocol was approved by Institutional Animal Ethics Committee reference no. IAEC/CVSc/P-03/2022. The animals were divided into four groups to evaluate the efficacy of decellularized scaffolds prepared from *Ficus benjamina* leaves for regeneration of full thickness skin defect. In group I the wounds were dressed with a sterile non-adhesive open mesh dressing. In group II autograft, In group III whole leaf decellularized scaffolds in three layer, In group IV powdered decellularized leaf scaffolds and bandaging was done in remaining groups as mention in group I.

Surgical procedure

Firstly, one hour before start of surgery body temperature of New Zealand white rabbits was taken by using the infrared digital thermometer (figure 1a). The animals were restrained in sternal recumbency and the dorsum (thoracolumbar region) of all the animals were depilated, scrubbed with one percent chlorhexidine, painted with 3% povidone iodine for aseptic creation of full-thickness skin wound (figure 1b). Wound creation was carried out under general anesthesia using 6 mg/kg xylazine hydrochloride followed by 60 mg/kg ketamine hydrochloride intramuscularly [18]. Anesthesia was maintained by additional doses of intravenous injection of ketamine hydrochloride, if required. Four full-thickness skin wound (20 mm x 20 mm each), two on the right and two on the left side, were created on the dorsum of each rabbit. A gap of 20 mm was kept between the two wound. Wound was created 20

Figure 1: Representative image of body temperature by infrared digital thermometer (a); aseptic preparation and scrubbing (b); full-thickness skin wound, open wound (I), Autograft (II), implanted with whole leaves decellularized scaffold (III) and crushed leaves decellularized scaffolds (IV) that is repaired wounds are covered with Cuticell™ C (c,d,e), in New Zealand white rabbits

mm away from the midline on either side of the dorsum. Hemorrhage, if any, was controlled by applying pressure with sterile cotton gauze. All four wounds of each rabbit were treated as: untreated control/ open wound (I), autograft (II), implanted with whole leaves decellularized scaffold (III) and crushed leaves decellularized scaffolds (IV). Subsequently, the repaired wounds were covered with wet surgical dressing containing 0.5% chlorhexidine (Cuticell™ C) (figure 1c, d and e). After recovery from anesthesia, rabbits were housed individually in properly disinfected cages. Further, antimicrobial treatment (Ceftriaxone 20 mg/kg intramuscularly once a day) and meloxicam (0.3 mg/kg intramuscularly once a day) was continued for five days. The efficacy of the grafts was evaluated on the basis of below mentioned parameters.

Clinical observations

General behavioural changes: Feeding pattern and general behavioural changes in all the animals were observed daily in the morning during the observation period.

Rectal temperature: Rectal temperature was recorded daily in the morning up to 14 post-operative days in all the animals.

Warmth of graft and adjoining area: The warmth of the graft and adjoining area was measured at day 0, 7, 14, 21 and 28 using Infrared digital thermometer.

Gross observations

The graft site was observed on day 0, 7, 14, 21 and 28 post-operatively for the evaluation of following parameters. Wound area was measured at day 0, 7, 14, 21 and 28 using graph sheet. Percent contraction with respect to the original wound size was calculated using the following formula.

Computerized planimetry (colour digital image processing)

Coloured photographs were taken on days 0, 7, 14, 21, 28 of healing with the help of digital camera at a fixed distance. Analysis of shape, irregularity and color of the lesions were determined (Color of graft: 1 Pink, 2 pinkish pale, 3 pale, 4 light brown, 5 dark brown, 6 black), Desiccation of graft (1 resembling normal skin, 2 slight, 3 moderate, 4 severe) Wound margins (1 pink, 2 brown, 3 black), Sloughing of graft: 1-not sloughed, 2-partially sloughed, 3-complete sloughed), Surface/marginal granulation (1 mild, 2 moderate, 3 severe), Scar (1 no scar, 2 mild, 3 moderate, 4 severe). The group having less gross observation scores was considered the best [19].

Haematological observations

Blood smears for differential leukocyte count (DLC) was prepared on 0, 7, 14, 21 and 28 post-operative days. The blood smears were stained with leishman stain for 15-20 minutes. The counting was expressed in per cent.

Evaluation of reconstruction potential of decellularized *Ficus benjamina* leaves scaffolds

Histological observation

The biopsy specimens were collected on days 7, 14, 21 and 28 post-implantation for the histopathological evaluation.

Hematoxylin and Eosin staining (H and E staining)

Hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) staining was used to observe and detect the cell infiltration (cytoplasm and nucleus components) within the regenerated tissue retrieved on days 7, 14, 21 and 28, following their implantation and samples were fixed in 10% formalin (10 ml formalin mixed with 90ml 1X-PBS) for 24 h and

then paraffin blocks were prepared from the samples. Then sections with a thickness of 6 μ m were cut by microtome. The paraffin embedded sections were fixed on glass slide, cleared in xylene-I and xylene-II for 2 minute each, rehydrated by decreasing the ethanol concentration from to 99.99% to 30%, washed with distilled water, dipped in hematoxylin for 7-8 minute. After washing, the slides were counter stained with eosin dyes for 2 minute, dehydrated by increasing the ethanol concentration, cleared in xylene and then mounted the slides. The sections from grafted area were observed under light microscope for epithelization (1 Present, 2 Partially present, 3 Absent), inflammation (1 Resembling normal skin, 2 Mild, 3 Moderate, 4 Severe), fibroplasia (1 Resembling normal skin, 2 Mild, 3 Moderate, 4 Severe), collagen fiber density (1 Denser, 2 Dense, 3 Less dense), thickness (1 Thicker, 2 Thick, 3 Thin) and their arrangement (1 Best arranged, 2 Better arranged, 3 Worse arranged, 4 Worst arranged) at the healing site [19].

Masson's trichrome staining

The tissue sample of grafted area was collected on days 7, 14, 21 and 28 post-implantation and sectioned in the same way that of histology sections. In this staining collagen takes blue color. The group having less histopathological score was considered the best.

4, 6-diamidino-2-phenylindole 2HCl (DAPI) immunostaining

The sections were also subjected to H and E, Masson's Trichrome stained micrographs were further confirmed by using DAPI (Elabscience) staining. The cell infiltration within the regenerated tissue on days 7, 14, 21 and 28, following their implantation were further confirmed by cold blue fluorescence observed in DAPI stained biopsy sample. The cellular and nuclear material having DNA in the biopsy tissue showed spots of cold blue fluorescence [20].

Scanning Electron Microscopic (SEM) analysis

Biopsy samples were retrieved on days 7, 14, 21 and 28 post-implantation for SEM [16].

Statistical analysis

The data analysis was performed using SPSS software version 18.0 (SPSS, Inc., Chicago, IL). One-way ANOVA (Analysis of variance) was used to compare the mean values of control and treatments. In addition, the Independent "t" test was used to compare the mean values between groups at different intervals.

Results and Discussion

Gross/macrosopic observations

Grossly, after treatment with SDS (5%) and TnBP (1%) and finally bleach by 4% sodium hypochlorite (36h). The colour of the leaves became translucent at 204h (120+48+36) time intervals (figure 2a). Sodium Dodecyl Sulfate (SDS) is an ionic detergent like and it solubilizes cell membranes and effectively removes the nuclear materials in shorter time frames compared to other chemical treatments [21]. Zwitterionic detergents such as tri-n-butyl phosphate (TnBP) share properties with both ionic and nonionic detergents. They have been shown to preserve the extracellular matrix (ECM), ultrastructure but tend to be limited in their ability to completely remove cellular content [22].

Histological observations

The transverse section of H&E stained micrographs of decellularized *Ficus benjamina* leaves showed that cuticle was completely removed from both adaxial and abaxial surface of

Figure 2. *F. benjamina* leaf scaffold prepared using 5% SDS and 1% TnBP and depigmented by 4% NaOCl (a); H & E stained (b); 4',6-Diamidino-2-phenylindole (DAPI) stained (c) and SEM image (d) of decellularized *F. benjamina* leaves scaffolds

epidermis. The palisade tissue was very well arranged and nucleus free. The absence of purple-blue dots and chlorophyll in the stroma of the leaves represent complete the process of decellularization (figure 2b). In H & E stained micrographs of native leaves tissues, nuclei were observed but they were abolished from the decellularized leaves [14].

DAPI staining

The results of H&E stained micrographs were further confirmed by using DAPI fluorescent immunostaining. The cellular and nuclear material having DNA in the *Ficus benjamina* leaf tissue after process of decellularization showed absence the spots of cold blue fluorescence that indicate the permanent elimination of almost all nuclear components from the native leaf tissues at 204h interval (figure 2c). Elimination of almost all DNA from the cells of the processed tissue is a crucial part in decellularization process [23].

Scanning electron microscopic study

The ultrastructure of decellularized *Ficus benjamina* leaf tissue was analyzed by SEM. While removing the nuclear and cytoplasm content of leaf samples, the morphological structure remained intact. After the decellularization process cuticular wax was completely removed according to the SEM images. There was no significant change in the topographical structure of the *Ficus benjamina* leaf tissue even after the decellularization (figure 2d). The topographical architecture of the leaf specimens did not significantly alter following the decellularization technique. Leaf samples' morphological structure was unaltered even after the cellular material was removed, proving that the primary objective was accomplished [24].

DNA quantification

Quantitative evaluation of residual DNA in the *Ficus benjamina* leaf tissues after process of decellularization showed a significant reduction in DNA content and the values for fresh and decellularized leaf was 111.28 ± 2.08 ng/ μ l and 14.26 ± 0.54 ng/ μ l, respectively. This result is below the generally acknowledged criterion of ≤ 50 ng/mg for suitably decellularized tissue [25].

Surgical procedure

Decellularized biological scaffolds composed of extracellular matrix (ECM), and derived from mammalian tissues, are widely used for clinical applications that involve repair and reconstruction of soft tissues. In the present study anesthesia was produced by intramuscular administration of xylazine @ 6 mg/kg body weight

and ketamine hydrochloride @ 60 mg/kg body weight. This combination provided good anesthesia for the creation of 20x20 mm² size full thickness skin defects and their repair with the whole leaves decellularized scaffolds and crushed leaves decellularized scaffolds in New Zealand white rabbits. No complication due to anesthesia was observed in any of the animals. Ketamine hydrochloride and xylazine hydrochloride combination has been used for creation and reconstruction of experimental wounds in rabbits [26]. All the animals recovered safely from anesthesia and recovery was smooth without any complication.

Clinical observations

General behavioral changes: Generally rabbits move here and there in the cages. After creation of wounds and transplantation of decellularized leaf scaffolds, the rabbits of different groups remained dull on the first day attained the haunched back posture in the corner of their cages, instead of their natural resting posture of sternal recumbency. Most of the animals of different groups started taking feed and water partially within 24h after surgery and feed and water intake became normal by 3rd post-operative day in all the animals. Dullness, depression and partial anorexia observed in the immediate postoperative period (1-2 days) may be attributed to surgical trauma (pain) and inflammation at the site of reconstruction [27].

Rectal temperature: The Mean \pm SE values of the rectal temperature ($^{\circ}$ F) were nearly normal or slightly decreased in all the group of animals on day one. It may be due to the effect of anesthesia. No significant change in the rectal temperature in different group of animals was noted at different time intervals. Comparison among groups also reveals no significant change in rectal temperature. The values of temperature in all four groups were found fluctuating within normal limits and close to base line values throughout the study period. In contrast to present study, the increase in rectal temperature after repair of cutaneous wounds with different decellularized *Ficus benjamina* leaf tissue was noted in New Zealand white rabbits [28]. Increase in rectal temperature in immediate postoperative period might be due to more surgical stress to the animals and may also be attributed to the action of endogenous or leukocytic pyrogen secreted by granulocytes, monocytes and macrophages [29].

Warmth

The results of mean \pm SE values of the warmth ($^{\circ}$ F) at the site of wound creation and subsequent graft implantation and adjoining areas at different time intervals in all the four groups are presented in figures 3a and b, respectively. The warmth of the wound/graft

Figure 3: Mean±SE of warmth of the wound/grafted area (a); Mean±SE of warmth of adjoining area (b); Mean±SE of wound area (mm²) (c) and Mean±SE of wound contraction (%) of different groups in New Zealand white rabbits at different time intervals (d)

area was significantly ($P < 0.05$) increased on day 7, 14 and 21 in group I, II and III animals and on day 7 and 14 in group-IV animals. However, warmth of the adjoining area was significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher on day 7, 14 and 21 in group I and II, and on day 7 and 14 in group-III and IV animals.

This increase in warmth either may be due to imbibition of angiogenic tissue within the graft or inflammation caused by surgical trauma. The vasodilation of the local wound vessels beneath the grafted tissue leads to increased blood flow resulting in increase in the temperature of the graft [30]. Contrary to this, significant ($P < 0.05$) decrease in warmth after reconstruction of skin defects in rabbits may be due to a thick crust formation over the wound surface [28].

Gross observations

Wound area and percent contraction

Surgical wounds appeared apparently healthy in all the animals of different groups throughout the period of observation. None of the wound showed any complication like infection or pus formation. The results of Mean±SE of the wound area (mm²) and total wound contraction (%) at different time intervals in various groups are presented in figures 3c and d, respectively. Although the original wound area created was 20x20 mm² but the wounds were slightly expanded in group I, III, and IV. In group I, no graft was used and wounds remained open whereas in group III 20x20 mm² patches of decellularized *Ficus benjamina* leaves scaffolds and in group IV the powder form decellularized leaves scaffolds were used for skin regeneration. As the healing progressed,

the wound area decreased significantly ($P < 0.05$) at different time intervals in all the groups. On day 7 wound area was significantly ($P < 0.05$) decreased in all the groups but decrease was highest in the full thickness wounds of group III animals as compared to other groups. On day 14 wound area further decreased significantly ($P < 0.05$) however it was minimum in group IV animals. On day 21, comparisons among groups revealed a significant decrease in wound area in group I and II animals and wound completely healed in group III and IV animals. Complete healing was recorded on day 28 in group II group III and group IV animals. The wound did not heal in group I at this time interval. Significant ($P < 0.05$) increase in percent contraction was observed in all the groups during the observation period. On day 14, maximum wound contraction (67.68%) was recorded in group IV animals where crushed leaves decellularized scaffolds were used. On day 28, complete healing was observed in group II, III and IV, except in group I. Wound contraction was in the centripetal direction to the wound margins that facilitates its closure during healing process. This phenomenon is carried out by myofibroblasts that contain α -actin and are mediated by contractile forces developed by granulation tissue from wound [31]. Wound healing rate can be defined as the gross epithelization of the wound area. Wound contraction was assessed by percent retention of the original wound area as reported by [32]. Wound contraction has been used for the assessment of wound healing process. Wound area decreased gradually as the healing progressed. On day 7, the contraction of the wound surface was highest in group III (Whole leaves decellularized scaffolds) animals as compared to the other group of animals which may be due to less vascularization in these groups as compared to the other groups. This causes the evaporative loss of moisture contents and

Figure 4: Computerized planimetry of open wound (Group- I)(a-e), autograft (Group- II) (f-j), decellularized leaf scaffolds in patches of 2cm² (Group- III) (k-o) and decellularized leaf scaffold 2cm² in powder form (Group- IV) (p-t) of *Ficus benjamina* leaves tissue at day 0,7,14,21 and 28 days of following implantation in New Zealand white rabbits

ultimately more contraction [28]. On day 28, in group I animals 96.35% wound contraction was recorded where standard surgical dressing material was used. Autograft showed less contraction in the healed wound when compared to the control open wound. All *Ficus benjamina* leaves scaffolds decreased the wound contraction and supported the formation of epidermis. Double layered skin regeneration showed significantly less wound contraction than the untreated wounds [33]. Effective inhibition of wound contraction by contractile fibroblasts has long been considered essential for optimal dermal regeneration in full thickness skin wounds [34]. Fibroblasts growth factor-2 (FGF2) may reduce wound contraction by inhibiting the phenotypic change of fibroblasts to myofibroblasts, which is likely involved in contraction [35]. Random orientation of the pores in the scaffold may prevent the remaining

myofibroblasts from contracting the wound area. When cells are randomly bound to the scaffold the sum of the contracting forces are near zero [36]. When living fibroblasts are entrapped within the matrix, a spontaneous contraction occurs after a few hours [37]. In group II wound showed less contraction as compared to group I which might be due to higher degree of acceptance of autograft by the wound bed. The graft remodeling occurs as a result of motile activity of fibroblasts migrating through the graft. The cultured fibroblasts particularly with a dermal support do not regress when transplanted to a living tissue [38]. The fibroblasts contribute to the wound healing process reduce the contraction of the wound and support collagen synthesis and neovascularization.

Computerized planimetry (colour digital image processing)

The representative colored digital photographs of open wound and wounds repaired with different grafts at different post-implantation days are presented in figure 4a-t. In group I on day 7, the surface of the wounds was covered with soft and fragile yellowish white mass having mildly desiccated top surface. By day 14, a clear cut thick crust developed on the wound surface and some part of crust was necrosed and sloughed off. On day 21, the crust detached off leaving a raw granular pinkish tissue. On day 28, severe contraction was observed leaving a small unhealed area. In group II on day 7, the autograft appeared light pinkish brown in color and slightly dried up and dehydrated, causing retraction of its margins and margins were pinkish at places. On day 14, the graft was firmly adhered with the underlying pinkish granulation tissue, but its margins were retracted. On day 21, the autograft adhered more firmly with underneath tissue and appeared imbibed by the host visibly and on day 28, the wound healed completely at this time interval. In group III on day 7, the top layer of whole leaves decellularized scaffolds was dark brown with formation of granulation tissue at one corner. On day 14, the scaffolds were firmly adhered with the granulation tissue of underlying whole leaves decellularized scaffolds. The boundaries of the top decellularized scaffolds retracted from the margins exposing healing tissue. On day 21, the wound was completely healed. In group IV on day 7, the top surface of crushed leaves decellularized scaffolds became light brown in color and the interface marked with reddened border, it got shrink slightly and seemed merged with the granulation tissue which was developed within the underlying crushed leaves decellularized scaffolds. On day 14, most of the part of the scaffolds was absorbed exposing granulation tissue. By day 21, the size of the wound got reduced and healed with no evidence of sloughing of the scaffolds. On day 28, the graft area seemed similar to the normal skin with no scar at the site. The results of group III and IV were comparable to the study conducted for assessment of the regeneration of the full thickness skin defects using decellularized skin scaffolds in rat and rabbit model [12, 39]. A dermal component provides an environment that promotes vascularization of the graft and fibroblasts play an active role in the replacement of dermal matrix [40].

Differential leukocyte count (DLC)

The results of Mean±SE values of differential leukocyte count (%) in treatment groups at different time intervals are shown in figure

5a and b, respectively. A significant ($P < 0.05$) increase in neutrophil counts after creation of wound and transplantation of graft/scaffold was observed on day 7 in all the animals of different groups. The peak values were observed on day 7 in all groups of animals. Contrary to increased neutrophil count, a significant ($P < 0.05$) decrease in lymphocyte count was observed on day 7 in all the animals of different groups. The changes observed in the eosinophil and monocyte count were non-significant ($P > 0.05$). The basophils were less than 1% in all the groups at different time intervals. The values of DLC were found within normal limits on day 28 in all groups.

The neutrophils act as the first cellular defense of the body and neutrophilia along with leucocytosis is generally occurs during inflammation [41, 42]. Therefore, the peak values were observed on day 7 in all the groups. Besides the increase in neutrophil count, there was also decrease in lymphocyte count which returned near to base line value by day 28 in all the animals of different groups. Moreover, DLC is proportional count of different WBCs where neutrophil and lymphocyte are major constituents. The DLC value revealed a significant increase in neutrophil percentage in early post-operative days with gradual return nearer to normaly, probably due to inflammatory response consequent to surgical trauma and foreign body reaction. The neutrophilia for short duration suggested the effect of surgical trauma rather than the implant provoked response. Similar observations were also reported by [43] following tension free hernioplasty using polypropylene prosthetic material.

Histopathological observations

Histopathological observations (Haematoxylin and Eosin staining, masson's trichrome stain) conducted on the biopsy specimens retrieved from the implantation on days 7, 14, 21 and 28, postoperatively are showed in figure 6a-p and figure 7a-p, respectively. The group having least number of score was considered the best. In group I on day 7, the wound was fully covered with necrotic tissues and debris infiltrated with neutrophils. The underlying stroma contained proliferated fibroblasts and moderate number of new blood vessels and had less dense, thin and worst arranged collagen fibers. At this stage the total histopathological score was 21. On days 14, the edges of the wound had partial epithelization and moderate inflammation with moderate number of new blood vessels and had dense, thick and worse arranged

Figure 5: Mean±SE Neutrophil count (%) and lymphocyte count (%) in New Zealand white rabbits of different groups at different time intervals

Figure 6: Histopathological observation of the graft biopsies of open wound (Group- I)(a-d), autograft (Group- II) (e-h), decellularized leaf scaffolds in patches of 2cm² (Group- III) (i-l) and decellularized leaf scaffold 2cm² in powder form (Group- IV) (m-p) of *Ficus benjamina* leaves tissue collected at day 0,7,14,21 and 28 days of following implantation in New Zealand white rabbits (H & E Stain, 20X)

Figure 7: Histopathological observation of the graft biopsies of open wound (Group- I)(a-d), autograft (Group- II) (e-h), decellularized leaf scaffolds in patches of 2cm² (Group- III) (i-l) and decellularized leaf scaffold 2cm² in powder form (Group- IV) (m-p) of *Ficus benjamina* leaves tissue collected at day 0,7,14,21 and 28 days of following implantation in New Zealand white rabbits (Masson's trichrome Stain, 20X)

collagen fibers. Total histopathological score was 18. On day 21, the changes were slightly less prominent than on day 14, except denser collagen fibers were seen on day 21. The score was 16 at this stage. On day 28, there was incomplete regeneration of the superficial epithelium and well formed stroma. The total histopathological score was 10. In group II on day 7, marginal epithelization was evident with stroma having moderate fibroplasia and degree of inflammation with less number of new blood capillaries. Collagen fibers were denser, thin and better arranged. The histopathological score was 19. On day 14, the changes were similar to day 7 except reduced degree of inflammation, mild degree of fibroplasia and moderate number of new blood capillaries. The collagen fibers were better arranged and the score was 15. On day 21, the epithelization and proliferation of stroma was similar to day 14 and score was 14. Epithelization started in skin adenexa and collagen fibers were sparsely arranged. On day 28, there was complete epithelization of the wound and the underlying stroma had mild fibroplasia with denser, thick and best arranged collagen fibers. The total score reduced to 9. In group III on day 7, whole leaves decellularized scaffolds (graft) showed severe necrotic changes and superficial scab was sloughed off. Inflammation and fibroplasia was moderate with mild neovascularization around the underlying graft and fibroblastic cells were seen invading the decellularized leaf scaffold. Collagen fibers were less dense, thick and better arranged. The total histopathological score was 18. On day 14, inflammation and neovascularization were less as compared to day 7 and debris of the decellularized leaf scaffold was evident at places. On day 21, the epithelization was still incomplete and underlying stroma had less dense, thick with best arranged collagen fibers and had few capillaries as compared with day 14. The decellularized leaf scaffold was completely absorbed. The histopathological scores reduced to 14. On day 28, epithelization was complete and inflammation had subsided. Fibroplasia was similar to day 21. Collagen fibers were denser, thick and best arranged and the total histopathological score reduced to 9. In group IV on day 7, there was no evidence of epithelization and the wound was covered with necrotic tissue infiltrated with mild inflammatory cells. The underlying crushed leaves decellularized scaffolds (graft) showed good infiltration of fibroblasts within the graft. Collagen fibers were dense, thin and better arranged with moderate neovascularization. The total histopathological score was 17. On day 14, inflammation was moderate with mild neovascularization. Collagen fibers were denser, thicker and better arranged and the total score reduced to 13. The decellularized scaffold was completely disintegrated and surrounded by the fibrous tissue and collagen fibers. On day 21, the epithelization was still incomplete and underlying stroma had evidence of neovascularization and less dense collagen fibers as compared with day 14. The decellularized scaffold was completely absorbed. The total score further reduced to 11. On day 28, epithelization was complete and inflammation was absent. Fibroplasia resembled normal skin with neovascularization and collagen fibers were best arranged. The histopathological score was 9 at this stage. This group showed lower score at different stages of healing.

Full thickness skin defects are characterized by a complete damage of the epithelial regenerative tissues that reside in the dermal region. In these defects, epithelization starts only from the edges of the wound. Size of the wound is a critical factor for epithelization and scar formation. Full thickness skin defect with more than 1 cm in diameter needs skin grafting or other alternative techniques to prevent excessive scar formation [44]. The primary component of plant material, cellulose, has been shown to be biocompatible as it is used in several medicinal applications [45]. The ideal graft is that should not elicit immune reaction, cover and protect the wound

bed, accelerate the healing process, decreases the pain and results in little or no scar formation. Many full thickness skin grafts became necrotic due to an impaired neovascularization [46]. Collagen scaffolds enabled faster migration of cells involved in skin wound healing. It readily integrates with the wound tissue and facilitates the attachment, migration and proliferation of cells on the wound site [47]. Acute inflammatory response showed infiltration of polymorphonuclear cells and subsequent loss of the graft material following implantation in rat model [48]. Moderate to severe inflammation, fibroblastic proliferation and new vascular tissue along with spilled neutrophil was observed in all the groups. The newly formed ECM was well spread out over the entire scaffold area in group III and IV. [49] also observed proliferation of fibroblasts within the decellularized scaffold and the bioengineered decellularized matrices. Inflammation is the important phenomenon for healing by combating infection and inducing the proliferation phase [50]. On day 7, group IV samples have least histological score (17). Although mild to severe inflammation and fibroplasia was present in all the groups, but it was minimum in groups IV. The early reduction of inflammation, as in case of groups III and IV, facilitate the process of wound healing in to the next phase. The grafts of groups III and IV were well tolerated by the host. The acellular grafts were invaded by the fibroblasts and underwent neovascularization without any evidence of immune reaction and rejection. These results were in accordance with [51]. Kim et al. observed that in full thickness skin wounds treated with small intestinal submucosal sponges, process of epithelization started by 14 days in rat model [52]. The decellularized grafts were under the process of resorption. In group II, the stroma had moderate fibroplasia with mild neovascularization and moderate degree of inflammation. These findings were in accordance with the results of [28]. On day 14, least histological scores were observed in group IV. Moderate to severe inflammatory changes were observed in groups I and II. Inflammation and denuded surface of wound constitutes a part of acute response following injury which results in coordinated influx of neutrophils to the wound site. Delayed healing in groups-I was might be due to more inflammation as compared to other groups. The release of growth factors and cytokines by the neutrophils, macrophages and mast cells increases inflammation at the wound site which may slow down the repair process [53]. Necrosis and sloughing of the superficial layer of graft was observed in groups III and IV. It may be either due to the desiccation of the superficial surface of the graft in high environmental temperature or due to an impaired formation of new blood vessels [46].

Meanwhile, the underlying granulation tissue increased in mass that pushed up the superficial decellularized leaves scaffolds (graft) upwards. Although, the animals of groups III and IV showed well-formed collagen and neovascularization but these processes were particularly faster and earlier in group IV. The proliferation and migration of epithelial cells are dependent on an adequate supply of oxygen [54]. Vascularization of the scaffolds from the patient's wound bed normally takes about 3 weeks [55]. In present study wound area was very narrow in group IV at this time interval as compared to other groups. The enhanced rate of wound healing and significant reduction in healing time might be due to enhanced epithelization. Nillesen et al. observed partial coverage of the wound area with some granulocytes on day 14 [33]. Purohit observed fibrous dermis showing feature of granulation tissue which was devoid of adenexal elements like hair follicles, sebaceous glands at day 14 in acellular dermal graft treated wounds in rabbits [30]. On day 21, histopathological score was least in group IV (11) and epithelization was partially present which are more or less similar to the normal skin. On day 28, all the wounds of different groups

Figure 8: DAPI (*4, 6-diamidino-2-phenylindole 2HCl*) stained pictures of the graft biopsies of open wound (Group– I)(a-d), autograft (Group– II) (e-h), decellularized leaf scaffolds in patches of 2cm² (Group– III) (i-l) and decellularized leaf scaffold in powder form (Group– IV) (m-p) graft on days 7, 14, 21 and 28, following their implantation in New Zealand white rabbits

were completely covered with epidermis except group-1. Collagen fibers were best arranged and oriented parallel to the skin surface in groups II, III and IV suggesting a better repair of the damaged tissue in these groups. Group IV had lowest histopathological score among all four groups

Nuclear staining

The cell infiltration within the graft on days 7, 14, 21 and 28, following their implantation was confirmed by cold blue fluorescence observed in DAPI (*4, 6-diamidino-2-phenylindole 2HCl*) stained biopsy sample (figure 8a-p). In group I on day 7, cold blue fluorescent images were generated in less in number (Less dense). On days 14, cold blue fluorescent images were generated less in number (Less dense). On day 21, the changes were slightly more prominent than on day 14, cold blue fluorescent images were generated moderate in number (dense). On day 28, the changes were more prominent than on day 21 and cold blue fluorescent images were generated more in number (denser). In group II on day 7, cold blue fluorescent images were generated in less in number (Less dense). On days 14, cold blue fluorescent images were generated moderate in number (dense). On day 21, the changes were slightly more prominent than on day 14, here cold blue fluorescent images were generated moderate in number (dense). On day 28, the changes were more prominent than on day 21 and

cold blue fluorescent images were generated more in number (denser). In group III on day 7, cold blue fluorescent images were generated in less in number (Less dense). On days 14, A distinct cell wall structure was observed, seen as a uniform thin cold blue fluorescent images were generated forming individual cavities of consistent size. On day 21, the changes were slightly more prominent than on day 14, less cell wall structure was observed which generated more cold blue fluorescent images (denser). On day 28, the changes were more prominent than on day 21 and cold blue fluorescent images were generated more in number (denser). In group IV on day 7, cold blue fluorescent images were generated in less in number (Less dense). On days 14, a distinct cell wall structure was observed, seen as uniform thin cold blue fluorescent images were generated forming individual cavities of consistent size. On day 21, the changes were slightly more prominent than on day 14, cold blue fluorescent images were generated moderate in number (dense). On day 28, the changes were more prominent than on day 21 and cold blue fluorescent images were generated more uniform (denser). On day 14 a distinct cell wall structure was observed for in group III and group IV conditions, seen as uniform thin blue fluorescent images forming individual cavities of consistent size. In all groups, the growth of host tissue of cells over the graft was similar. On day 28, the images were generated for every sample had same cold blue fluorescent. Interestingly, similar observations were made of the

Figure 9: Scanning electron microscopic (SEM) pictures of the graft biopsies of open wound (Group- I)(a-d), autograft (Group- II) (e-h), decellularized leaf scaffolds in patches of 2cm² (Group- III) (i-l) and decellularized leaf scaffold 2cm² in powder form (Group- IV) (m-p) of *Ficus benjamina* leaves tissue collected at day 0, 7, 14, 21 and 28 days of following subcutaneous implantation in New Zealand white rabbits. Specimens were observed under SEM at 10 kV using 2000x magnifications with scale bar = 10µm

cellulose structure in the DAPI staining images in rat kidney slice [20].

Scanning electron microscopy

The cell infiltration within the graft on days 7, 14, 21 and 28, following their implantation was examined with H&E stained, adhesion of collagen fiber confirmed by masson's trichrome staining and contains of nuclear material(DNA) was proved by DAPI staining (4, 6-diamidino-2-phenylindole 2HCl) of biopsy sample. Further SEM examination was conducted to authenticate the results obtained by the above parameters (Figure 9a-p). In group I on day 7, the depositions of collagen fibers had less dense, thin and poorly arranged and some proliferative cells was observed. On days 14, the edges of the wound had partial depositions of collagen fibers with moderate number of growing cells and had some dense, thick and worse arranged collagen fibers. On day 21, the changes were slightly more prominent than on day 14 with depositions of some dense collagen fibers. On day 28, depositions of collagen fibers were best arranged, with some rounded proliferative cells were found mostly on the top surfaces with the highest density in aligned direction on the collagen fiber. In group II on day 7, surface was covered with a significant amount of a glossy material, indicating the development of new regenerated collagen fibers. The thin collagen fibers in low density with some cross-linking were observed.

Stroma showed moderate no of growing cells. On day 14, the changes were similar to day 7 significant amount of proliferative cells. The growth of cells was found mostly on the top surfaces of scaffolds with the highest density in aligned direction on the collagen fibers. The collagen fibers were worst arranged. On day 21, the thick collagen fibers and some proliferation of stroma observed similar to day 14 and collagen fibers were sparsely arranged. On day 28, there the underlying stroma had denser, thick and best arranged collagen fibers. In group III on day 7, whole leaves decellularized scaffolds (graft) SEM images showed that the tissue surrounding leaf displays an overall extensive colonization with concurrent depositions of collagen fiber. Collagen fibers were less dense, thick and least arranged. On day 14, the changes were similar to day 7. The pores of the underlying graft were filled with stroma and growth of fibroblasts into scaffolds matrix at host graft junction was observed. The growth of new cells was observed on the top surfaces of leaf scaffolds with the highest density in aligned direction on the collagen fibers. The collagen fibers were least arranged. On day 21, the thick collagen fibers and some proliferative cells and growth of fibroblasts in stroma were observed and collagen fibers were better arranged. On day 28, there the underlying stroma had denser, thick and best arranged collagen fibers. SEM images show overall surfaces were covered with a significant amount of a glossy material, indicating the development of new regenerated collagen fibers and dense collagen fibrous meshwork that resemble

to normal skin. In group IV on day 7, (graft) SEM images showed that the powder leaves decellularized scaffolds tissue covered with concurrent depositions of thin collagen fiber. Collagen fibers were less dense, thin and least arranged. On day 14, the changes were similar to day 7. The pores of the underlying tissue were filled with stroma and growth of fibroblasts was observed. They usually appeared large and round, but sometimes they were oval or spindle shaped. The collagen fibers were least arranged. On day 21, the growth of new cells was observed on the top surfaces of leaf scaffolds with the highest density in aligned direction on the collagen fibers. The growth of the thin collagen fibers in stroma was observed. On day 28, there the underlying stroma had denser, thick and best arranged collagen fibers. Collagen fibers in low density with some cross-linking were observed. SEM images show overall surfaces were covered with a significant amount of a glossy material, indicating the development of new regenerated collagen fibers and dense collagen fibrous meshwork that resemble to normal skin. The results clearly demonstrate that in groups II groups III and groups IV SEM images here displaying the strong attachment to surfaces of the host tissue. However, in all groups the SEM images show an overall surfaces were covered with a significant amount of a glossy material, indicating the development of new regenerated collagen fibers and dense collagen fibrous meshwork. Fibroblasts were infiltrated within the pores of graft. The growth of cells was found mostly on the top surfaces of scaffolds with the highest density in aligned direction on the collagen fibers. They usually appeared large and round, but sometimes they were oval or spindle shaped. This was probably also the reason their outer surfaces appeared irregular [56].

Conclusions

The results of this study concluded that powdered leaves decellularized scaffolds was found best followed by decellularized leaves scaffolds for the reconstruction of full-thickness skin defects in New Zealand white rabbits and can hasten the wound healing rate and quality.

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